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Thermodynamic modeling of ^{90}Sr migration with alkaline groundwater at the Chernobyl NPP industrial site

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SUMMARY

Thermodynamic modeling of monitoring studies on well 4-G, which was located on the industrial site of the Chernobyl nuclear power plant, was performed. In the range of pH 9.5 - 12.5, an increase in the concentration of strontium in the form of SrOH^+ and a decrease in the form of Sr^{2+} was noted in the groundwater, against the background of an increase in the volumetric activity of ^{90}Sr by 200-500 times to 550 Bq/l. The reason for this was an increase in the ionic strength of solutions >5 mmol/l.

Introduction.

It is generally accepted that almost 100% of ^{90}Sr is removed from alkaline groundwater due to soil sorption (Singh *et al.*, 2009). Studies of ^{90}Sr migration with underground waters of the Chernobyl nuclear power plant site (Lytvyn *et al.*, 2016; Panasyuk & Lytvyn, 2017; Panasyuk *et al.*, 2015, 2018), on the contrary, show that with the formation of a strongly alkaline environment in underground waters, in which $\text{pH} > 9.5$, a noticeable (200-500 times) increase in the volumetric activities of ^{90}Sr is observed. At the same time, in some wells, the concentration of ^{90}Sr can increase to 700-2100 Bq/l. Laboratory experiments simulating Sellafield groundwater (Wallace *et al.*, 2012), indicated that in unbuffered ($\text{pH} 5.5$) and HCO_3^- -buffered ($\text{pH} 7.2$) groundwater, the extent of ^{90}Sr sorption increased significantly, up to 61, 8% and 98.9%, respectively. Between $\text{pH} 6 - 8$, pH , almost complete ($> 99\%$) sorption of ^{90}Sr in sediments occurs. However, even in strongly alkaline conditions, when the ionic strength of the solution increases to more than 5 mmol/l, the sorption properties of sands and loamy sands decrease. At the same time, remobilization of ^{90}Sr adsorbed on soils occurs by cation exchange. That is, there is no unambiguously defined behavior of ^{90}Sr in alkaline groundwater according to literature data.

In the work, with the help of thermodynamic modeling, some issues of migration of ^{90}Sr with groundwater are explained.

The purpose of the work is to determine the forms of ^{90}Sr in groundwater depending on the pH of the solution and the influence of ionic strength on the migration ability of radiostrontium in the aquifer of the Chernobyl nuclear power plant site.

Method and Theory

The study of the migration forms of ^{90}Sr was carried out using a set of software tools "Geochemist's Workbench Community Edition". To confirm and understand the migration processes, modeling of the spread of various ^{90}Sr complex compounds such as SrCO_3 , SrHCO_3 , SrSO_4 , SrOH^+ , SrNO_3^+ from the 4-G well groundwater was carried out.

Basically, such programs from the Geochemist's Workbench complex as GSS - The Geochemist's Spreadsheet and SpecE8 were used for data analysis.

Since GSS - The Geochemist's Spreadsheet is a full-featured spreadsheet, it was used to sort, organize, and further process the data. (Bethke *et al.*, 2022).

With the help of SpecE8, the calculation of various forms of ^{90}Sr was performed, as well as the ionic strength of the solution (ISS) of groundwater from the 4-G well was calculated.

Using the method of geochemical statistics, a correlation analysis of the dependences between the ionic strength of the solution and the activity of ^{90}Sr was carried out (Kovalenko *et al.*, 2021).

Examples

The work, as an example, uses the results of observations on the 4-G well, which were carried out as

Figure 1 Value of pH and ^{90}Sr volumetric activity in groundwater samples from a well 4-G

part of radio-hydroecological monitoring. The series of observations of pH dynamics and volumetric activities of ^{90}Sr can be conditionally divided into three periods (Fig. 1): Period I - pH value in the range of 7.5 - 8.5; Period II - pH value in the range of 8.5 - 9.5; Period III - pH value in the range of 9.5 - 12.5.

As can be seen from Fig. 1, at the pH of groundwater typical for period I, the average values of ^{90}Sr concentration are at a low level. When the pH is increased to 8.5 - 9.5 (period II), the average values of the volumetric activities of ^{90}Sr begin to decrease further. The reasons for the

decrease in ^{90}Sr concentrations are that at pH 8.3 - 8.5, part of the hydrocarbonate ions transforms into carbonate ions, which in turn form insoluble compounds with calcium ions and strontium ions, which can fall out of the groundwater solution in sediment (Panasyuk et al., 2011). However, at a pH higher than, mainly, 9.5 (period III), the volumetric activity of ^{90}Sr increases sharply (see Fig. 1).

The values of pH, volumetric activity of ^{90}Sr and chemical composition in samples from wells 4-G (Table 1) for the sampling dates chosen to represent their periods (12.03.1998 – Period I, 02.05.2002 – Period II and 02.23.2006 – Period III).

The concentration of $\text{Sr}_{\text{stab.}+\text{radioactive}}$ is assumed to be conditionally the same (value = 1 mg/l) for experiments in all periods in order to compare changes of different forms of ^{90}Sr .

Real values of the volumetric activity of ^{90}Sr in groundwater samples (Table 2).

SpecE8 was used to calculate $\text{Sr}_{\text{stab.}+\text{radioactive}}$ concentrations in different forms, depending on the period of observation in well 4-G. The concentration of SrCO_3 gradually increases until the third period. (Table 2). The concentration of SrHCO_3 , on the contrary, decreases. The concentration of SrSO_4 increases in the second period, but decreases in the third, SrOH^+ increases in the third period, and Sr^{++} (Fig. 2) and SrNO_3^+ decrease. Also, in the Period III, a significant, more than 2 times, increase in the ionic strength of the sample is observed (Fig. 3).

Table 1 Chemical composition, pH and ^{90}Sr volumetric activity in samples from wells 4-G

Nomenclature of definitions	Period I	Period II	Period III
	03.12.1998 (mg/l)	05.02.2002 (mg/l)	23.02.2006 (mg/l)
pH	6.75	9.15	11.3
Na^+	17.1	26.9	58
K^+	16.4	7	50
Ca^{++}	12	4	24
Mg^{++}	4.8	1.5	4.9
NH_4^+	1.1	1	4.5
Cl^-	4.76	2.8	6.4
SO_4^{2-}	24.6	28.8	24.7
NO_3^-	6.5	0	2.4
NO_2^-	0	1.5	3
HCO_3^-	85.4	51.9	45.8
CO_3^{2-}	0	9	118.5
Oxidability	20.4	16.8	13.12
SiO_2	10.86	22.83	10.9
PO_4	5	11.25	0.86
F	1.22	3	1.4
Mineralization	172.60	134.40	342.2
$\text{Sr}_{\text{stab.}+\text{radioactive}}$	1	1	1
^{90}Sr , Bq/l	10	8	540

Table 2 Calculated forms of ^{90}Sr in groundwater samples, depending on the period of monitoring observations on well 4-G.

Forms of ^{90}Sr	Period I	Period II	Period III
	03.12.1998 (mg/l)	05.02.2002 (mg/l)	23.02.2006(mg/l)
SrCO_3	2.00E-04	0.03893	0.2427
SrHCO_3	0.01969	0.01518	6.89E-04
SrSO_4	0.06126	0.07511	0.04412
SrOH^+	2.88E-07	7.11E-05	0.008235
Sr^{++}	0.958	0.9311	0.827
SrNO_3^+	8.64E-04	-	2.51E-04
Ionic strenght (mmol/l)	2.721	2.272	5.73

The increase in strontium concentrations in the third period coincides with the increase in ISS. At an ISS of more than 5 mmol/l, a significant increase in the volumetric activities of ^{90}Sr is observed. Thus, we can state that the increase in ISS of groundwater contributes to the reduction of ^{90}Sr sorption by soils and its remobilization from the surface of soil particles due to cation exchange by analogy with (Wallace et al., 2012). As well known, ISS is a measure of the intensity of the electric field created by the ions in the solution. Probably, with the beginning of period III, there is a change in the surface charge of soil particles from negative to positive, during which cations cannot be sorbed, but, on the contrary, must be remobilized. And $\text{pH} = 9.5$ is probably the point of zero charge (pzc). The study of the relationship between the concentrations of ^{90}Sr and ISS in groundwater samples by the method of geochemical statistics (Kovalenko et al., 2021) showed the presence of a high correlation (Fig. 4). Correlation coefficient $K=0.87$ ($K=1-P$, where P is a well-known P-criterion)), that is, there is a close relationship between ISS and ^{90}Sr concentrations in water samples from well 4-G.

Figure 2 Concentrations of Sr^{++} and SrOH^+ depending on the pH according to the data of thermodynamic modeling of the monitoring results for the 4-G well

Figure 3 Concentrations of ^{90}Sr and ionic strength of the solution in samples from well 4-G

Figure 4 Correlation between ^{90}Sr bulk activity and ionic strength in groundwater samples from well 4-G

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Conclusions

It was determined that an increase in ISS of groundwater up to 5 mmol/l leads to a 200-500-fold increase in the volumetric activity of ^{90}Sr in strongly alkaline groundwater, in which, as a rule, strontium sorption by soils reaches 99% (Singh *et al.*, 2009). This result corresponds to the conclusions (Wallace *et al.*, 2012), which were obtained as a result of experiments in laboratory conditions.

An increase in the ISS of strongly alkaline groundwater leads to a decrease in the sorption properties of soils, and to the remobilization of adsorbed ^{90}Sr through cation exchange with groundwater.

The results of thermodynamic modeling show that for pH values >9.5 the concentrations of Sr^{2+} in the form of strontium ion decrease, and in the form of SrOH^+ they increase. The same data were obtained (Wallace *et al.*, 2012). At the same time, strontium in groundwater in the form of SrOH^+ becomes dominant at pH > 11. According to the results of the presented work, the dominance of SrOH^+ concentrations over Sr^{2+} does not occur.

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